

Research Article

Effect of jigsaw learning strategy on performance and retention in organic chemistry among senior secondary school students in Kontagora, Niger state

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Abstract

This research work examined the effects of jigsaw teaching strategy on organic chemistry academic performance and retention in senior secondary schools in Kontagora, Niger state. The study adopted a Quasi-experimental research design involving pre-test, post-test and post-posttest non-equivalence control group design. The population comprised of 1,129 senior secondary II school students in Kontagora. The sample size for the student was 88 (Experimental 46 and control 42). Organic Chemistry Performance Test (OCPT) was used to collect data for the study the instrument was validated by experts and the reliability coefficient was determined to be 0.82 using Kuder Richardson formula (KR-20). Data collected were subjected to analyses at two different levels; descriptive and inferential levels. At descriptive level, mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions raised. At inferential level, Independent sample t-test was used to test the null hypotheses formulated at $\alpha \leq 0.05$ level of significant. Findings revealed that there is significant difference between the performance mean scores of students taught organic chemistry using JIGSAW learning strategy and those taught using conventional method in favour of the experimental group. Also, there is significant difference between the retention ability of students taught organic chemistry using JIGSAW learning strategy and those taught using conventional method in favour of the experimental group. It is recommended amongst others that adoption of jigsaw teaching strategy is necessary to address the current poor performance of students in chemistry and organic chemistry in particular, also Chemistry teachers should be encourage through training and re-training programmes by state Ministry of Education and Professional bodies such as STAN by organizing seminars and workshops for Chemistry teachers on how to address difficult concept like Organic Chemistry.

Keywords: Chemistry; Organic Chemistry, Academic, Performance, Retention, Jigsaw Teaching Strategy.

1. Introduction

Chemistry is a discipline that contributes to the upliftment of human living standards through the provision of health and other social amenities. It is one of the disciplines upon which technological advancement hinges (Broman & Pardman, 2014). Chemistry knowledge and skills are put in use in field of human endeavour such as agricultural engineering, space science, biotechnology, pharmaceutical industry to mention but few (Junture, 2015). It was as a result of this recognition accorded chemistry in the development of individual and the nation that has made it the central science and branch of pure science that deals with composition of matter and the principles; Kenya Institution of Education (2015) sees chemistry as a pre-requisite for offering science oriented courses in the tertiary institution and the knowledge obtained provided students with valuable

concepts. Chemistry education contributes to society's development by helping students to develop into more responsible citizens who should help to build a strong economy, society, healthier environment and thus bring about a brighter future. It is the vehicle through which chemistry knowledge and capacity is build (Junture, 2015). One of the concepts in Chemistry taught at secondary school is the Organic Chemistry.

Organic chemistry which is the main focus of this student is the chemistry of carbon compounds and has been found very useful in different fields of science and technology. Organic chemistry has made a lot of contribution to the welfare of mankind in various fields. Examples of these contributions are in the industry sector especially in beer brewing, petrochemicals and widely used in medicine

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(Ngoka, 2015; Meni, 2014). In spite of the importance of chemistry generally and organic chemistry in particular, students' performance and retention in chemistry are declining as recorded by Oloruntegebe, (2014). He also noted that not only are the result of chemistry (organic chemistry) getting worse but also the recipients are getting progressively unscience in their approach to solving scientific problem. Approaches used in teaching chemistry had been recognized as one of the variables adding to poor execution in the subject (UNESCO, 2014).

For instance, the WACE Chief Examiners' Report revealed that the performance of candidates in chemistry paper 2, that contain organic questions as 2022 with mean scores of 28 and standard deviation of 13.78 was worse than candidates' performance in 2021 with mean score of 47 and standard deviation of 13.78. This analysis denotes a decrease in the performance of student in chemistry (Organic Chemistry in Particular for those years. This analysis agreed with the research of Kozma and Russcline Pekdag (2016) and Kwuka and Samuel (2017) that chemistry is seen as an abstract subject that is difficult to understand. This is because the basic concepts in organic chemistry have to be mentally visualized by the students to understand chemistry phenomena.

The quality of instruction received by the students depends on the knowledge of the teacher. There is a strong positive relationship between teachers' level of knowledge of subjects and levels of subject knowledge achieved by their students and levels of subject knowledge achieved by their students (Sophia, 2016). Therefore, for any subject to be effectively taught, there should be trained and qualified teachers employing appropriate instructional strategy. This implies that for the effective study of chemistry, teachers have to select appropriate instruction methods that will appeal to both the students, arose their interest and enable them achieve excellent performance. Sophia, (2016) stated that reliance on the conventional teaching method has been criticized as modeling student into passive recipient to information transmitted by the teacher and making them highly dependent on the teachers for much of their learning needs. This deficiency calls for a corresponding change in chemistry less on delivery method that could engender more fun and integrative class sessions like Jigsaw teaching Strategies.

The JIGSAW Teaching strategies (JTS) is a method of organizing classroom activity that make students depends in each other to succeed. It breaks a class into groups and breaks assignment into piece that the group assembles to complete the puzzle Jigsaw, one of the cooperative learning techniques, is based on group dynamics and social interactions (Sahin, 2016).

This technique includes two different treatments in different small groups in order to help learning and improve

cooperation among students.

Several empirical studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of Jigsaw teaching strategies (Garonia, 2016). However, no study has relatively assessed the effect of JTS on students' performance and retention in organic chemistry in senior secondary school students in kontagora local government.

In spite of this, organic chemistry has been one of the central aspects of the chemistry curriculum in senior secondary school, yet students' performance in the topic has continued to remain low in many schools, including those in Kontagora, Niger State. From classroom teachers, Nwafor, Okonkwo & Onuigwe (2023) WAEC chief examiners report (2020-2023), and school-based assessments, it is often reported that students tend to view organic chemistry as very abstract, not easy to visualize, and difficult to remember over time. These learning difficulties have been linked to the persistent use of traditional lecture-based approaches that offer minimal opportunities for students to engage actively with the content, discuss among themselves, and build their knowledge.

Despite the fact that a number of studies have indicated an improvement in performance and retention in various science topics with cooperative learning strategies, especially the Jigsaw method, such as Mohammed & Muhammed (2019), Nwankwo, (2021) and Azeez (2022) very little is known about how their effectiveness stacks up for teaching organic chemistry in Kontagora senior secondary schools. Furthermore, studies undertaken so far have been confined to other subjects, different regions, or limited sample sizes, making it uncertain whether their findings are generalizable to this locality. A complete lack of empirical evidence on this issue within Kontagora leads to a pedagogical decision-making gap for chemistry teachers and education planners desiring evidence-based ways through which underperformance in organic chemistry could be addressed.

The problem, therefore, of this study is the inadequacy of empirical evidence to establish whether the jigsaw teaching strategy can significantly enhance the performance and retention of students in organic chemistry in senior secondary schools in Kontagora, Niger State. This calls for a controlled experimental investigation student taught with Jigsaw and those taught with conventional lecture methods. it is hoped that the findings of this study will help provide solution to the problem of this study.

The following objectives were stated to guide this study:

- (i) Examine the differences between the performance scores of students taught organic chemistry using the Jigsaw Teaching Strategy (JTS) and those taught using the conventional method
- (ii) Find the difference in the retention scores of students taught organic chemistry using Jigsaw Teaching Strategy (JTS) and those taught using the conventional method.

The following research questions were considered:

1. What is the difference between the performance mean scores of students taught organic chemistry using Jigsaw Teaching Strategy (JTS) and those taught using

conventional method (TM) in Kontagora, Niger State?

2. What is the difference between the retention mean scores of Students taught Organic Chemistry using Jigsaw (JTS) and those taught using conventional Teaching Method (CTM) in Kontagora, Niger State.

The following null were formulated and tested at $\alpha \leq 0.05$ level of significant:

H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of secondary school students taught organic chemistry using Jigsaw teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method

H_{02} : There is no significance difference between the mean retention scores of secondary school students taught organic chemistry using Jigsaw teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method.

2. Methodology

In this study, quasi-experimental research design involving pre-test, posttest and post-posttest non-equivalent control group design was used for the study. Two groups of students participated in the study; Experimental and control groups. The experimental group was taught organic chemistry using JIGSAW strategy for a period of six weeks while the control group was taught the same concept and periods using conventional method. After the administration of the treatment, posttest was administered to determined the effect of JIGSAW on students' performance. At two weeks interval, post-posttest was administered to determined their retention ability.

The population comprises all 1,129 SS II chemistry students in public senior secondary schools in Kontagora, Niger State. A total sample of 88 students was drawn from the population using purposive sampling technique by

selecting schools with comparable facilities, qualified teachers, and similar academic calendars was used to assigned the schools into experimental and control groups using simple random sampling technique

Organic Chemistry Performance Test was adopted by the researcher from WAEC past questions. The OCPT comprised multiple-choice and short-answer items designed to measure both students' performance and retention ability.

The instrument was validated by experts in the department Chemistry Education. The reliability of the OCPT was determined to be 0.82 using Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20).

Prior to the administration of the treatment, pretest was administered to the groups to determine their equivalent level. . During the treatment, the experimental group was taught organic chemistry using the Jigsaw Cooperative Learning Strategy for a period of 6 weeks. The control group was taught the same concept using conventional method for the same period of time. Posttest was administered to the groups to determine the effect of JIGSAW on students' performance. At two weeks interval, the same test was given was administered to the two groups to determine their retention ability.

The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while ANCOVA was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

3. Results

3.1. Test for equivalence of pre-test scores

Table 1 shows the t-test comparison of pretest scores of experimental and control groups.

Table 1: t-test Comparison of pre-test Mean Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Test	Group	N	df	X	SD	t-value	P
Pre-test	Experimental	46	86	45.43	9.67	4.65	0.00
	Control	42		55.21	10.05		

Significance at 0.05 level

An examination of the table shows that P-vale (0.00) is less than 0.05 alpha level ($P < 0.05$). This means there was a significance difference between the mean scores of the two group ($t(86) = 4.65$, $P < 0.05$). Pretest was used as covariate in testing all the hypotheses through the use of Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA).

3.2. Answers to research Questions

3.2.1 Research Question 1

Research question 1: What is the difference between the mean performance scores of Secondary School students taught organic chemistry using JIGSAW teaching strategy (JTS) and those taught using Conventional Teaching Method (CTM) in Kontagora, Niger State.

Table 2 : post-test Mean Scores of Students Exposed to Jigsaw teaching Strategy (JTS) and Conventional Teaching method (CTM)

Group	N	Mean (x)	SD
Jigsaw Teaching (Experimental) Strategy	46	75.67	8.00
Conventional Teaching (Control) Method (CTM)	42	67.00	6.43

Table 2 shows that the students exposed to Jigsaw teaching strategy has a mean score of 75.67 with standard deviation of 8.00 while those students exposed to conventional teaching method had mean scores of 67.00 with standard deviation of 6.43. This implies that the students exposed to Jigsaw teaching strategy performed better than

those exposed to conventional teaching method.

3.2.2 Research Question 2

Research Question 2 : What is the difference between the mean retention scores of Secondary school students taught organic chemistry using Jigsaw (JTS) and those taught using conventional Teaching Method (CTM) in Kontagora, Niger State.

Table .3: Difference between the mean retention scores of students taught Organic Chemistry using JTS and those taught using CTM

Group	N	Mean (x)	SD
Experimental (Jigsaw Teaching Strategy)	46	65.20	7.60
Control (Conventional Teaching Method)	42	56.77	6.78

It is revealed from table above that the experimental group exposed to Jigsaw teaching strategy had a higher mean score of 65.20 and standard deviation of 7.60 of retention in organic chemistry while the conventional teaching method had mean scores of 56.77 and standard deviation of 6.78. This implies that the Jigsaw teaching strategy here much influence on students retention level than the conventional teaching method.

3.3. Hypotheses Testing

3.3.1 Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of secondary school students taught organic chemistry using Jigsaw teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method.

Table 4. ANCOVA results on the mean performance score of the experimental and control group

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Correct model	1661.8301	2	830.915	15.475	.000
Intercept	15386.996	1	15386.996	286.563	.000
Convariate (pretest)	1556.764	1	778.382	14.50	.000
Main Effect (Treatment)	1425.066	1	1425.066	26.540*	.000
Error	4564.068	85	53.695		
Total	456533.000	88			
Correct Total	6225.898	87			

3.3.2 Hypothesis 2

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant different between the mean retention scores of secondary school students

taught organic chemistry Jigsaw teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method

Table 5: Summary of ANOVA on mean retention of the experimental and control groups

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Between Groups	1558.669	1	1.558.669	29.879	0.000
Within Groups	4486.241	86	52.166		
Total	6044.910	87			

Table 5 shows the ANOVA results of the post test scores of experimental and control groups. The table shows that the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 alpha level, $F(1,87) = 29.88$. on the bases of this, hypotheses two was rejected. The result revealed that there was significant difference between the retention level of experimental group exposed to organic chemistry with Jigsaw teaching strategy and those exposed to conventional teaching method in favour of Jigsaw teaching strategy.

3. Discussion

The findings revealed that the mean performance scores of students taught with jigsaw teaching strategy achieved higher than those taught using the conventional teaching method. This findings agreed with that of Maxwell (2014) that Jigsaw instructional strategy significantly improves students' academic performance in government. Similarly, the study was in line with the study of Danladi (2015) that Jigsaw instructional strategy has significant effects on students' performance in senior secondary schools biology contents. This means that students performance meaningfully in chemistry as a result of Jigsaw teaching method and that the method was adequate for the instruction process.

The findings of this study agreed with the finding of Mari and Sani (2015) that the use of cooperative learning strategy has significant effect on the academic performance of formal 'reasoners' more than that of the concrete reasoners. Also, the findings of this study was in support of the finding of Adejoh (2015) that Jigsaw instructional technique has more effects on students' performance and transferability in Economics that the group investigation. The difference in mean was further tested for significance. The result from hypotheses testing reveal that there is significant difference in the mean, performance scores of secondary school students taught organic chemistry using Jigsaw teaching strategy and those taught using the conventional Teaching method. This was in favour of Jigsaw group. This finding was in line with the finding of Danladi, (2015) that there is a significant difference in the mean performance scores of biology students taught using the Jigsaw instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method.

This finding also supported the finding of Inuicha, Eneogu, Asogwa and Ngwuchkwu (2016) that the use of

Jigsaw instructional strategy and conventional teaching

method is significantly different. Invariably, these findings shows the effectiveness of Jigsaw teaching strategy as a method for enhancing academic performance regardless of the subject matter and level of class. The findings from result reveal that the mean retention scores of students taught using the conventional teaching method. This finding supported the finding of Gibbad (2014) that cooperation learning on students' retention of 6th grade primary school pupils in mathematics concept is higher than those taught using conventional teaching method. The findings agreed with the finding if Isa (2014) that students taught by cooperative learning has a higher performance score and higher retention scores more than the control group taught by lecture method.

5. Conclusion

The study however, showed that Jigsaw teaching strategy helped to improve students' academic performance and retention in hydrocarbon part of organic chemistry than students taught using the conventional method. In facts, Jigsaw teaching strategy has demonstrated its effectiveness in increasing meaningful learning in organic chemistry because it is an active-oriented method which involved checking and assessing individual academic confidence level at every new stage or units in knowledge without leaving a stone unturned. It is therefore, recommended that all level of education should adopt Jigsaw teaching strategy because it boosts the participation of students in organic chemistry thereby improving the academic performance and retention of students in organic chemistry.

Recommendations:

The following recommendations were put forward based on the findings of the study

- It is recommended that adoption of jigsaw teaching strategy is necessary to address the current poor performance of students in chemistry and organic chemistry in particular,
- Chemistry teachers should be encourage through training and re-training programmes by state Ministry of Education and Professional bodies such as STAN by organizing seminars and workshops for Chemistry teachers on how to address difficult concept like Organic Chemistry.

Abbreviations

OCPT	Organic Chemistry Performance Test
JTS	Jigsaw Teaching Strategy
CTM	Conventional Teaching Method
ANCOVA	Analysis of covariance

Author Contributions

Olalere, Joshua: Conceptualization, methodology, Writing-original draft,

Bila, Khadija Adamu: Writing- Review and Editing

Agbenyeku, Peter: Methodology, Writing- Review and Editing,

Conflicts of Interest

The author(s) declare that they have no known competing financial interests, professional affiliations or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper,

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